

Effect of K application on yield and total P and K uptake. Meghalaya, India.

Treatment	Grain (t/ha)			Straw (t/ha)			Total K uptake (kg K/ha)			Total P uptake (kg P/ha)		
	Submergence	Drainage	Mean	Submergence	Drainage	Mean	Submergence	Drainage	Mean	Submergence	Drainage	Mean
T1 (no K)	2.2	2.1	2.1	3.8	3.6	3.7	68.90	67.90	68.40	4.98	4.81	4.89
T2 (33 kg K/ha)	2.9	2.1	2.5	4.4	4.9	4.6	89.70	92.20	90.90	7.11	5.47	6.29
T3 (66 kg K/ha)	3.5	2.9	3.2	5.0	4.8	4.5	120.70	97.30	109.00	7.06	5.74	6.40
T4 (99 kg K/ha)	3.9	4.0	—	7.0	8.0	7.5	162.70	184.00	173.00	9.32	10.91	10.11
Mean	3.1	2.8	—	5.0	5.1	—	110.40	110.30	—	7.12	6.73	—
CD (0.05) for K	0.2			0.4				8.10			0.34	
CD (0.05) for water management treatment	0.1			ns				ns			0.48	
CD (0.05) for K × water management treatment	ns			0.5				ns			ns	

Effect of K application on K, P, and Fe contents in rice shoots. Meghalaya, India, 1985.

spots at the base of the leaves. The spots coalesced to give a bronze appearance, then leaves developed marginal tip burning. Plots with more than 66 kg K/ha were almost free from such disorders and exhibited luxuriant vegetative growth and better grain filling.

Grain and straw yields increased significantly with increasing K levels (see table). The greatest yield response was with 99 kg K/ha. Yield differences might be attributed to the effect of K on alleviating K and P deficiencies as well as Fe toxicity in the plants (see figure).

K content increased with increasing K and was more pronounced at flower initiation. P content increased with K application, while Fe concentration was drastically reduced, indicating K-P synergism and K-Fe antagonism.

The highest K and P uptake were with 99 kg K/ha. Fe concentration was drastically reduced in grain with each increase in K.

Grain yield and K concentration ($r = 0.78^*$), K:P ($r = 0.72$) and K:Fe ($r =$

0.96^*) in shoot at flowering, and K concentration in straw ($r = 0.80^*$) all had significant correlations. K concentration in rice shoot or in straw could be used as simple tools for predicting yield response to K. □

Response of lowland rice to Zn

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We studied the effect of Zn on yield under lowland situation at the Regional Research Station, Semiliguda, Koraput, during 1979 kharif. Soil was clay loam

Effect of Zn on rice yield. Semiliguda, Orissa, India, 1979.

Method	Zn conen (ppm)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Control	0	4.2
Seed soaking for 12 h	454	4.5
	908	5.0
Seedling root dip for 12 h	454	4.6
	908	4.4
Foliar spray at maximum tillering	454	4.6
	908	4.7
CD (0.05)	—	0.1

(Haplaquept) with pH 6.2, 0.829% organic C, and 0.86 ppm DTPA-extractable Zn (slightly above critical deficiency). Two levels of Zn sulfate, 454 and 908 ppm Zn, were used for seed soaking, seedling root dip, and foliar

spray at maximum tillering. The experiment was in a randomized block design with four replications.

Rice variety Pankaj responded well to Zn treatment (see table). Seed soaking with 908 ppm Zn produced the highest

yield, followed by foliar spray at the same concentration. At 454 ppm Zn, both seedling dip and foliar spray produced identical yields. Root dip with 908 ppm Zn yielded the lowest. □

Effect on rice yield of nursery treatments at various levels of main field phosphorus

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We evaluated the effect of 6 nursery treatments and 3 field treatments of P

on characters of 25-d-old seedlings and grain yield of TKM9 rice. Soil was a Sandy loam with pH 5.3 and 308-11.4-112.8 kg available NPK/ha. The experiment had a factorial randomized block design and was replicated three times.

Nursery application of diammonium phosphate (DAP) at 2 kg/40 m² and superphosphate + urea equivalent to 2 kg DAP/40 m² significantly influenced

seedling height, leaf number, root length, and N uptake (Table 1). Basal application of 2 kg DAP/40 m² to the nursery was best and yielded highest (Table 2).

The different levels of P applied to the field did not influence grain yield significantly, perhaps because of the existing P status of the soil. The study indicates the advantage of transplanting DAP-treated rice seedlings. □

Table 1. Effect of nursery treatment on TKM9 seedling characters Tamil Nadu, India, 1984 kharif.

Nursery treatment	Seedling height (cm)	Leaves (no./seedling)	Root length (cm)	N uptake (g/m ²)
Control (no fertilizer)	18.1	4.2	9.6	2.6
Potassium dihydrogen phosphate (1%)	18.3	4.4	10.0	3.1
Diammonium phosphate (DAP) (2 kg/40 m ²)	30.2	5.5	13.6	6.0
Farmyard manure (FYM) (50 kg/40 m ²)	19.4	5.3	12.2	3.2
Superphosphate + urea (N and P equal to 2 kg DAP)	28.2	5.3	12.0	6.4
Root dipping of seedlings in superphosphate slurry (5%)	18.6	4.6	9.1	3.1
CD (0.05)	1.5	0.4	0.5	0.5

Table 2. Effect of nursery treatment and main field P application on grain yield and plant characters.^a Tamil Nadu, India, 1984.

Treatment	Panicles (no./hill)	Panicle weight (g)	Filled grains (no./panicle)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)
<i>Nursery treatment</i>					
Control	8.1	1.9	69	24.5	4.02
seed treatment with potassium dihydrogen phosphate (1%)	8.0	2.1	68	24.5	3.99
DAP (2 kg/40 m ²)	9.4	2.4	88	25.6	4.89
Farmyard manure (50 kg/40 m ²)	7.7	2.0	73	24.4	4.10
Superphosphate + urea (N and P equal to 2 kg DAP/40 m ²)	9.0	2.4	89	25.1	4.53
Root dipping of seedlings in superphosphate slurry (5%)	7.9	2.1	71	24.2	3.96
CD (0.05)	0.4	0.2	6	0.5	0.16
<i>Field treatments</i>					
No P (control)	8.1	2.1	75	24.6	4.20
11 kg P/ha	8.5	2.2	77	24.6	4.29
22 kg P/ha	8.6	2.2	78	24.8	4.26
CD (0.05)	0.3	ns	ns	ns	ns

ns = nonsignificant.

Integrated nutrient management for short-duration rice

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The effects on IR50 yield of individual and combined applications of *Azospirillum* and organic manure with various N levels were compared during 1986 kharif at RRS. The experiment in a split-plot design was on sandy loam with pH 6.8, EC 0.43 dS/m, and 297-18-

Effect on rice yield of organic manure and bio-fertilizer application with various levels of N.^a Tamil Nadu, India, 1986.

Treatment	Rice yield (t/ha)				Mean
	No N	49 kg N/ha	73 kg N/ha	98 kg N/ha	
Control	3.2	3.8	3.9	4.1	3.8
Farmyard manure (5 t/ha)	3.3	3.7	4.0	4.4	3.9
<i>Azospirillum</i> (2 kg/ha)	3.3	3.9	4.1	4.2	3.9
Farmyard manure + <i>Azospirillum</i>	3.2	3.8	4.1	4.5	3.9
Mean	3.3	3.8	4.0	4.3	
CD					
Biofertilizer × organic matter					–
N level					0.2

^aN was applied per soil test recommendation, with 98 kg N/ha as full dose.